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REMOTE LABORATORIES IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION. DERIVING GUIDELINES FOR THEIR IMPLEMENTATION AND OPERATION

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ABSTRACT

Exploratory laboratories are fundamental to engineering education, since they enable students to apply theoretical subjects to practical situations. The ongoing technical innovations are rendering remote laboratories possible. However, their implementation and operation encounter several challenges. This contribution gives an overview about the experiences gained throughout the project ELLI over a time period of 8 years. In 2012, a whole variety of remote laboratories was set up. At Ruhr-University Bochum, they are associated with Civil and Environmental Engineering, Mechanical Engineering, and Electrical Engineering and Information Technology. At TU Dortmund University, they are related to manufacturing processes, especially forming technology. To avoid individual software solutions, LabVIEW was set as standard tool throughout all applications. To summarize the experiences made, a final evaluation study was conducted in 2018 and 2019. The research design of this evaluation comprised a non-standardized survey method: From October 2018 to September 2019, a total of 11 expert interviews was under-taken with research assistants and professors. The interviews followed a semi-structured guideline which had previously been developed in a focus group discussion, containing five categories of leading questions. The transcribed interviews were analyzed via qualitative content analysis. This contribution presents challenges as well as potential for the use of remote laboratories in engineering education, in order to make the experiences gained available to the scientific community and to encourage further exchange about the use of digital innovations.

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1 INTRODUCTION & BACKGROUND

The current trend of remote experimentation provides new possibilities to enhance engineering education. Right now, different types of remote experiments, virtual and physical, are available. Hence in this publication, the term remote laboratory defines laboratories once there is a remotely operated experimental setup involved. Remote experimentation is used in several different disciplines with the main usage in electrical and control engineering [1,2], where downsized model plants are often used [3]. In this publication, laboratories in the field of mechanical engineering are dealt with. To provide a remote experiment, remotely controlled machinery, infrastructure to connect the laboratory to a public network, management systems for user scheduling, as well as experimental data transfer and storage, are needed.

The investigated remote laboratory in this study is developed as a part of the German project ELLI. This project is a collaborative effort at the RWTH Aachen University, TU Dortmund and Ruhr-University Bochum to improve the available methods for engineering education. In continuation of the results published in [4], which are based on the results from the remote laboratories at the Ruhr-University Bochum (RUB) alone, this research is focused on the remote laboratory at the TU Dortmund (TUD). At RUB, several laboratories were developed by different institutes and chairs of the engineering faculties, whereas the laboratory at TUD represents a more extensive and interconnected laboratory developed by the Institute for Forming Technology and Lightweight Components (IUL). The following paragraph gives a short description of the development team and the laboratory. More specific details can be found in [5]. The main components are depicted in Fig 1.

Fig 1. Fully automated tele-operative testing cell for material characterization as in [5]

The remote laboratory allows for the conduction of different experiments, featuring a tensile test stand (1), and a cupping test stand (2), both of which are fundamental for material characterization in mechanical engineering. The machines, robots (4), and microcontrollers (5) are connected by an overlaying control and safety system (6), which is based on the software LabVIEW, and an optical measuring system (3). Nowadays, access to the remote lab is provided by a self-developed control and user management platform. The development team was and still is a multi-disciplinary one comprising manufacturing engineers, mechanical engineers as well as automation and IT specialists. This paper deals with the development of the laboratory during the last 8 years, the lessons learned and compares them to results derived from the study

conducted at RUB. Thus, 8 years of experiences of two collaborating universities are shared, covering different kind of remote laboratories. The results are combined to extend existing guidelines for lecturers wanting to develop new remote laboratories from the ground up or based on their existing machines.

2 RESEARCH DESIGN OF THE LABORATORY EVALUATION

A qualitative study with expert interviews was conducted as described in [4]. In summary, the interviewees were questioned “based on their role as an expert for a certain field of action” [6], concerning 5 different topics. These topics are listed in Table 2. A semi-structured guideline with open questions was used for the interview that covered all stages from the initial planning phase to the permanent implementation in education. Follow-up questions were asked whenever the interviewer felt that certain aspects remained unmentioned or if certain answers needed elaboration. The interviews were recorded via a voice recorder, transcribed, and analyzed by qualitative content analysis [7]. Therein, information was categorized according to analytical categories defined before the beginning of the investigation and subsets for each analytical category were formed. All the while, the analysis remained open to the dynamic formation of new categories or restructuring of subsets. The final categories and subsets were compared to the aspects found in [4], adding one further category.

Table 1. Categories of interview guidelines

Topic 1	General questions and history of the remote laboratory
Topic 2	Planning phase of the laboratory
Topic 3	Development and implementation
Topic 4	Conducting experiments
Topic 5	Conclusions and outlook

3 RESEARCH RESULTS / LESSONS LEARNED

The results were categorized using the aspects found in the study at RUB: technical and technological challenges, didactic concepts and learning objectives, and project management. An additional category dealing with the long-term implementation of the remote laboratory was added. First, the findings at TUD are presented and then compared to the study conducted at RUB. This gives insight into similarities and differences of the development of several smaller remote laboratories compared to the development of a single larger laboratory.

3.1 Technical and technological challenges

In this section, the findings and experiences regarding the implemented technology are presented. The main technical elements mentioned in the interview were automation and control of both hardware, which includes machinery, cameras as well as control units, and software components, graphical representation of the laboratory, and safety measures to protect hardware and personnel.

Findings at TUD: The physical components were chosen from commercially available hardware. This focused the development on the required software and controls, which in its current properties contains several years of development. For control and automation of the equipment, the trial-and-error method sometimes had to be used to

achieve compatibility between hardware and software even though the installed communication protocols were known, leading to highly complex systems. Due to the complexity of the systems, a self-developed platform was created. It functions as a user management and scheduling system and allows for the control of any number of experiments allowing the team to work on both systems separately. It also redirects validated users to other webpages, being the graphical user interface (GUI) for the remote laboratory. Executable commands are integrated by buttons and input fields enabling the choice of values for the experiments.

The integrated safety measures prevent damage to personnel as well as to the equipment. A hardware-oriented system, which is disconnected from the remote-controlled system, functions as an emergency shutdown if detecting movement near the equipment. It requires a manual restart after each emergency shutdown. The software-based safety measures restrict experimental parameters to safe limits of the machinery and predefined movement of the robots, preventing misuse of faulty use. Operation is only possible when both systems are active and no error is present. Additionally, the systems only allow the transition between safe states of operation informing the user about invalid actions and denying their execution.

Comparing both universities: It became apparent that the complexity of the remote laboratories was a challenging factor. Therein, it was distinguished between the complexity of the user interface and the complexity of the underlying control system. To create a stable system, certain limitations and simplifications had to be made at both universities. This became especially apparent for some laboratories at RUB, where experiments had to be significantly altered from the way they were conducted as hands-on experiments. The laboratory at TUD was chosen for easier “remotization”, i. e. transition into remote operability. It already was highly automated, thereby lost almost no sensory feedback, and needed less alteration in general. At RUB, the aim was to conduct “usual experiments” as remote experiments, while at TUD, a highly automated experimental setup was chosen for degree of realism and increased learning potential. At RUB, most laboratories relied on some level of abstraction, while at TUD, an interface design was chosen to approximate the students being in the laboratory as realistic as possible, incorporating video streams and experimental raw data. In all cases, the learning objectives and target audience played a huge role in the design of the user interfaces. Finally, during the study at RUB, most interviewees stated that nowadays they would also recommend integrating more sensory feedback into the interfaces. At both universities, the implemented safety measures were implemented on the hardware as well as on the software side of the labs. For all labs, they imposed limitations and restrictions on the experimental setup. However, maintenance efforts were decreased simultaneously, ensuring long-term operation of the labs. The long-term operability of the system was in all cases established by a reduction of selectable process parameters. The safety measures also include means for an emergency shutdown via the user interface or through the hardware at any time during the experiment. After every emergency shutdown, a manual reset is required to guarantee the analysis of the shutdown, and to prevent the same error in the future.

3.2 Didactical concept and learning objectives

The didactical elements presented in this section are considering the inclusion of students' perspective, collaboration with experts in didactics, graphical representation

needed for education, students' preparation for the experiments as well as the utilization of the remote experiment as a teaching tool.

Findings at TUD: The targeted audience is Bachelor's students of mechanical engineering, mechanical engineering informatics, industrial engineering, and logistics. The students' perspective was considered through the team's reflection and experiences, as most of the team took the same course of study. Still, it was recommended to acquire the opinion of students for the final touch of the development. From the beginning, a didactical team supported the technical team by advising the selection of experiments, discussing learning objectives, improving the utilization of the remote laboratory, and by continuously evaluating the learning outcomes. The principal learning objective was determined to having the students learn how to use this remote laboratory to answer scientific questions instead of learning how to operate the equipment. A setup was chosen for which the limitations due to the safety measures only slightly differ from the hands-on version. This enhances the focus on the learning objectives as only actions aligning with the learning objectives are allowed. Additionally, the control of the GUI was designed as faithful as possible to the hands-on experiment to create a realistic impression of "being in the lab. Each student is granted a limited time slot, therefore groups need to combine relevant data and have to apply project management skills. Required background knowledge from lectures is examined in a digital quiz before the start of the experiment. Finally, before the conduction of experiments, an introduction into the control and user management platform and the GUI is available by presentation and video tutorials.

Comparing both universities: The initial target audience for the remote laboratory at TUD was students in the Bachelor's program only, while the initial target audience at RUB also included students in the Master's program. However, for testing purposes the remote laboratory at TUD was first used in the international Master's pre-course due to smaller group sizes. The students' perspective was rarely asked for in the design of the GUIs, as most teams consisted of (former) students or student assistants. Yet in this study, it was recommended to integrate the students' perspective during the final development of the user interface, thereby preventing uncertainties in explanations about control and concepts. A difference was found considering the cooperation with didactic experts for higher or engineering education. At RUB, the members of the engineering faculties rated their expertise in teaching as sufficient and stated that the required understanding of highly complex measurement techniques was most important in deriving appropriate teaching approaches. On the other hand, the team at TUD continuously cooperated with a team of didactic experts in the development of the laboratory. Concerning the required levels of automation and usability, those were similarly high at both universities. This potentially enabled users to conduct experiments without understanding the involved mechanisms. Due to this, the original learning objectives had to be adjusted and the focus was shifted from understanding and executing of a measurement technique to the gathering of experimental data and the subsequent evaluation. At TUD, those learning objectives were already defined at the beginning with the didactical teams' support. As a final point, some of the developers at RUB expressed it to be unlikely that a remote experiment can fully replace a hands-on experiment. Mentioned reasons regarded the importance of the more comprehensive, yet mostly unnoticeable, safety measures, absent development of manual skills, and faulty perception of time. The team at TUD

also regards their laboratory as valid and comprehensive substitute, that is yet best used in combination with additional hands-on experimentation.

3.3 Project management

Lessons learned regarding project management, i. e. dealing with teamwork and knowledge management, time management and unforeseen delays are summarized.

Findings at TUD: During the development phases, the teamwork changed from more individual work to shared work. Regular team meetings were used to discuss recent and pending developments. This has proven to be useful in times when research assistants were leaving or joining the team due to their expiring contracts. Additionally, some team members have worked on the project almost from the beginning. This shared knowledge allowed to only document successful ideas, and to omit ideas that had proven to be unfeasible due to too high effort.

Time management was often impaired by external factors, which sometimes necessitated the reduction of self-imposed aims to keep the development on time. Adjustments to the safety measures have proven to be especially time-consuming. According to the interviewees, a full work-year has been needed until the laboratory was able to be used, and then only in its most fundamental functionalities. Concerning overall project management, the effort proportionality for each new development idea had to be carefully evaluated. Alterations to initial concepts were only feasible if they enabled a reduced effort for a high number of cases. On the other hand, student theses being related to the development of specific aspects of the remote laboratory were a welcome addition.

Comparing both universities: For all laboratories, the initial schedule experienced delays because of unforeseen challenges. The requirements for the development of hardware or software solutions were often underestimated by the research staff and lead to significant delays for most projects. For some of the more complex laboratories at RUB, the learning contents, as well as the hardware, had to be downsized and adjusted multiple times during the development. The choice of a technical and didactical suitable laboratory at TUD rendered these iterations unnecessary. The setup of a remote laboratory demands interdisciplinary skills working together, from the respective field of engineering in which the laboratory is used, electrical and control engineering, and automation as well as programming. The interviewees often mentioned that additional expertise therefore had to be acquired. During the interviews at RUB, it was recommended that at least one person should oversee the project and work on it during its entire development time gaining knowledge in the required fields and additionally serving as a form of documentation. The developments at TUD serve as an opposite example, since the mixed team of mechanical engineers, programmers, automation engineers, and electrical engineers reported no such problems. This allowed for easier setup of the experiments and a stricter focus on the control system and didactical aspects. For all laboratories, the interviewees mentioned that standard procedures for documentation are not suitable and need to be adjusted. In this study, the interviewees stated that developments and new possibilities were discussed in the whole team and only successful developments were documented. As a final aspect, the team at TUD had at least one team member working on the project for the entire time. This helped accumulate and store knowledge about the project, and it positively influenced the documentation.

3.4 Long-term implementation

This fourth and final paragraph contains lessons learned about the transition to a permanently operated and maintained remote laboratory as well as other beneficial aspects regarding the development and synergistic effects.

At TUD, the fully developed remote lab, initially demanding huge effort, significantly reduces staff's workload and operational costs by dispensing with the need for safety and operating instructions and the provision of personal protective equipment for every participant. Due to its limitations relating to safety measures and the learning objectives, the remote laboratory is unfit for conducting scientific research. Yet, the equipment is extensively used for scientific research and student research projects in its hands-on version, requiring only slight modifications. This generates synergistic effects or a "second use-case". This „second use-case" contributes to the preservation of the remote laboratory beyond its funding phase since the equipment still generates scientific value in their standard, non-remote operation mode. Therefore, arrangements between educators and researches have to be made regarding the scheduling of remote experimentation and scientific research. Hence, the remote laboratory configuration has to be restored after each research period. In the interviewees' opinion, applying for research funding should become more likely to succeed in combination with educational context as a second-use case for expensive machines. Developing a remote lab with already available equipment should focus on such equipment that is scientifically used with sufficient downtime for educational purposes and control units that are easily configured for remote control.

4 CONCLUSION: RECOMMENDATIONS FROM LESSONS-LEARNED

The qualitative study via expert interviews has proven to be a suitable method for this evaluation as it allowed for responsive questions, which lead to the fourth category not explicitly mentioned in the previously conducted study. The conclusions drawn from this study and the comparison to the previously conducted study are given in the form of recommendations for others interested in the task of developing remote laboratories.

As technology advances and software solutions regarding connectivity and remote control has become more and more available features in recent years, the effort of developing new laboratories is significantly reduced. Still, the required complexity of the remote laboratory should be discussed and its effort-to-use ratio should be evaluated carefully. This transition might necessitate an adjustment of learning objectives. In the following, guidelines regarding encountered technical challenges are given:

- For "remotizing" a lab with new or already existing equipment, use hardware that already features remote operability, Alternatively, begin with available open source software packages to connect existing machinery via well-defined interfaces. In both cases, direct support from the manufacturers is recommended.
- Separate laboratory control from user management, e. g. by utilizing a central content management platform. This provides the benefit of being able to work on both systems in parallel and to integrate further laboratories via the same interfaces.

- Integrate safety precautions both on the software- and on the hardware-side. Restrict the selection of parameters to ensure the equipment, and to provide staff's safety. In addition, enable an automated shutdown in case of faulty operational states or parameters.
- Use the safety measures to enhance the focus on learning objectives, by denying executions of faulty decisions and giving appropriate explanations.
- Incorporate adequate sensory feedback (i. e. video- and audiostreams or animated process visualizations) to give a realistic impression of "being in the lab". Use those to sharpen the focus on the learning objectives, e. g. process visualization, control algorithms, or analysis of experimental data.

In remote laboratories, no direct feedback from supervising instructors is available, therefore the didactical approach has to be appropriately well-defined. Recommendations regarding the didactical concepts are listed in the following:

- Cooperate with experts in didactics to evaluate your laboratories' potential for "remotization". Already highly automated setups are preferable.
- Define targeted audiences and create learning objectives for each one. Incorporate those into the user interfaces, only depicting necessary features. Start this process already before starting the technical development.
- Provide instructions for the handling of remote systems, especially for experiments that can be repeated a limited number of times only.
- Integrate feedback from the targeted audience into the final designs of user interfaces and the systems' instructions. Evaluate the system with a limited testing group first.
- Consider the remote laboratory as a tool to enable further didactic methods and see it as an extension rather than a replacement to traditional laboratory work.

The development of a remote laboratory can be a time consuming task requiring high effort. Therefore, several aspects regarding project management are recommended:

- Appoint one or more persons in charge for the whole period of the expected development time, especially when team member exchanges are common practice like in German higher education.
- Assemble an interdisciplinary team, consisting of programmers, electrical, control and automation engineers.
- Discuss and document recent and current developments in regular intervals, to facilitate knowledge management throughout the project.
- As time management has proven to be very challenging, define a multi-layer approach and start by implementing base functionalities of the laboratory, which can be improved later. Also, a generous scheduling of the project is recommended.
- (Optional) Concerning necessary approvals of changes of infrastructure or safety measures in your laboratory, retain flexibility by specifying what you want to achieve. Still, remain as unspecific as possible regarding the chosen methods, as unforeseen changes might later become necessary.

The transition of the developed remote laboratory into permanent operation at the chair needs to be rated as beneficial, despite the necessary maintenance effort. To achieve this aim, the following recommendation are given:

- Remote laboratories should reduce workload and operational cost by not requiring supervision or safety instructions for students. Carefully consider the costs of a full automation against having to take manual action from time to time.
- Increase the nominal operating hours by also conducting scientific research in the laboratory, probably in a slightly less restrictive mode of operation.

Finally, partial developments of remote laboratories can be used for student theses, giving students the chance to work on a real project and acquiring additional skills in an interdisciplinary field. All in all, remote laboratories can be greatly beneficial to students' education and, despite the initially high effort, reduce costs and workload of the staff in the long-term.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Winzker (2019); Vision Remote Lab: <https://fpga-vision-lab.h-brs.de/weblab/login> [checked on April 21, 2020]
- [2] Lustig, F., Dvořák, J., Kuriščák, P. (2019), Professional and hobby hands-on-remote experiments, AIP Conference Proceedings, Vol. 2152, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5124764>
- [3] Technical University Ilmenau (2019): <https://www.goldi-labs.net/index.php?Site=2> [checked on April 21, 2020]
- [4] Strenger, N., Frerich, S. C. (2020), How To Design Digitalized Laboratories? Lessons Learned From Implementing Virtual and Remote Labs, Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Remote Engineering and Virtual Instrumentation, Athens, Georgia, USA, (in press)
- [5] Grodotzki, J., Ortelt, T. R., Tekkaya, A. E. (2018), Remote and Virtual Labs for Engineering Education 4.0 – Achievements of the ELLI project at the TU Dortmund University, Procedia Manufacturing, Vol. 26, pp. 1349-1360
- [6] Kaiser, R (2014): Qualitative Experteninterviews: Konzeptionelle Grundlagen und praktische Durchführung. Springer Verlag, Berlin Heidelberg, p. 35f
- [7] Mayring, P. (2010): Qualitative Inhaltsanalyse. Grundlagen und Techniken. 11., aktualisierte und überarb. Aufl., Beltz & Gelberg Verlag, Weinheim, p. 49f